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Abstract:

Hadoop is an open source system. It can handle millions of files to store in it. In Hadoop, we can store and process a large amount of data without having any limits. In now-a-days, business or an organization may create a million, billions of a data per day. so they must store these data using a hadoop.

keywords: Hadoop common, HDFS, YARN, MapReduce.

INTRODUCTION:

Hadoop is a JAVA based programming language. Hadoop was discovered by Doug cutting and Mike cafarella in the year 2005. The name comes as HADOOP, because the toy name of his child was an elephant. It supports the processing of large amount of data for free, industry based work such as to store the data and process the data, without limits. This is called as Big data. In hadoop, it does take any data as larger. It can store, process and analyzes the hundreds of terabyte and petabytes of data on cluster of a computer.

DEFINITION FOR BIG DATA:

Big data means huge data, it contains a sets large VOLUME, VARIETY of data and accessing at faster VELOCITY. In organization, big data can help to analyze the data, visualize the data in their business based goals. Big data's are measured in both terabyte, petabyte and also in Exabyte.

HADOOP COMMON:

Hadoop common can support other hadoop projects. In hadoop common, it includes file system.

hadoop common

HADOOP DISTRIBUTED FILE SYSTEM (HDFS):

Hadoop Distributed File System(HDFS) is used to store a data, when the connections are failures in namenode, datanode and network. HDFS stores files with metadata and application data separately. HDFS store metadata in an particular server (dedicated server) is called as Datanode and application data's are stored other server is called as Namenode. HDFS consists of master and slave architecture, in which master part controls the slave parts.

Architecture of HDFS:

DataNodes:

Depending upon the instruction from Namenode, it will perform the request such as read, write, creating a block, deleting a block and repulsion. Datanode are storing a file in an separate file system and it could not create a file in a same directory .

Repulsion:

All files are stored in a HDFS as a sequence of block. All blocks sizes are configuring to a file. namenode receives all reports from datanode called as block reports.

Namenode:

The file can be divided into large parts of blocks and each block is independently given to each datanodes. In namenode, files can be represented by in odes.

HDFS client:

Users can access the files by using an HDFS clients. The user can create, delete a file and also to read and write in files or directories.

If a client wants to read a file means namenode contain datanodes. In that datanode, user can directly contact with datanode and request can send to particular block and a task will perform. HDFS allow to know about location of blocks, these can be accessed by a Map reduce.

Four design principles are:

- It can be used to store a very large amount of data's. so storage capacity is large.
- If any redundancies are available means it can work against it, so the system is reliable.
- It does not affect, when transferring a large amount of data. so it can process a large amount of data.
- It can process sequentially according to batch wise.

YARN(Yet Another Resource Negotiator):

The yarn can be classified into Resource manager, Node manager, Application master and container.

Resource Manager: Application is sent to the resource manager by a client.

Node Manager: It contains slaves, (i.e) Application master and container. Node manager gives the storage details to resource manager.

Application Manager: It shows the status of a process and monitor a program.

Container: It is used to store a process in a desired way such as memory, cpu, disk for execution of a specific task.

In yarn, it can support with a cluster of 10000 nodes up to 2000 crores of nodes. YARN contains a separate resource manager with application management. in this application map reduces acts as an user space application, when YARN was deployed. so we can use map reduce in YARN on the same cluster with new version of map reduce is possible.

WRITING AN APPLICATION IN YARN:

- i) **Application client protocol:** The clients give an protocol for their project to a resource manager. The application should be submitted. In YARN client library, it can convert the protocol into simply a format for using the application.

ii) **Application Master protocol:** The application master will communicate with Resource manager about the protocol of the user. API allocates a resource manager and a resource manager client to perform the process.

iii) **Container manager:** The application master communicates with the Container manager to start a process, when the process is finished means stop the process by using a Node manager to complete this task.

MAP REDUCE:

The map reduce is used to distribute the files efficiently for computing. The main use of map reduce is splitting a large data into small data by using an intermediate solution. In map reduce, we can write an algorithm for a problem, which is divided into small programs to solve the problem after completing the process then it can combine it to large programs.

In a map reduce, contain an two blocks. (i.e) map and reduce.

In a map part it can split the large input data into a number of intermediate parts and the Reduce part is used to transform an intermediate part into output data's. Computational work can be occurred in both structured and unstructured programs.

Map reduce functionality:

It contain two nodes depending upon a cluster. They are

- *Job tracer
- *Task tracer .

i) Job tracer(Master):

It is responsible for jobs ,which can be send it to the slaves to perform and watch the slave process, if any problem happens in executing means it will re executing the task.

ii) Task tracer(Slave):

It performs the operations(process), which was given by a job tracer.

Map procedure:

It can divide the large problem into smaller problems and distribute these problems to workers. After the work completed it send the program to master. Worker will do this task, till the work is completed.

Reduce procedure:

If the task was completed, the answer for the sub problems from a master node will be combined to get an original problem.

How to map reduce works:

FOR EXAMPLE: If we give an input into two files. such as,
 file 1: “hai friend, hai how are you”?
 file 2: “hai friend, how was the day”?

Three operations are carried in map reduce. They are *Mapper, Combiner, Reducer*.

file 1 sends to a map:	file 2 sends to a map:
< hai,1>	<hai,1>
<friend,1>	<friend,1>
<hai,1>	<how,1>
<how,1>	<was,1>
<are,1>	<the,1>
<you,1>	<day,1>.

Mapper functions:

In a mapper, it can maps the input values by using an intermediate file. we can create 100 maps in a program, there is a parallelism for splitting a program.

Combiner functions:

In combiner, it can give a permission to the mapper to interact with other files.

<hai,2>	<hai,1>
<friend,1>	<friend,1>
<how,1>	<how,1>
<are,1>	<was,1>
<you,1>	<the,1>
	<day,1>.

In each file, it can eliminate the repetitions. so it can convert hai into 2 times.

Reducer functions:

In reduce functions, it can give all pairs having a same values should be reduced and then value are executed. so the output for above example is,

<hai,3>
 <friend,2>

<how,2>

<are,1>

<you,1>

<was,1>

<the,1>

<day,1>

Here, reduce an intermediate values, which was given twice and trice. It will arrange them in a ascending or descending format. Job reduces will be performed by a reduction engine. we could not sorting the output. It will perform according to the below steps:

I)It will shuffle the output, which is coming from a mapper.

II)Sort the inputs, which is coming as a output from a mapper.

III)Reducer will leave the same values, it taken only once.

In a **Hadoop** , the process will follow **First In First Out(FIFO)**.

Constraints followed in a map reduce:

It will “skip the nodes”, when a map failures occurs.

Reduce operation does not work, till mapper complete its function.

If a data contain a index page means, it should work faster than a map reduce function without an index page.

The larger program can be split up into smaller ones, so reduce function has a small data, when compared to the map function.

Advantages for using a hadoop:

It can split the large data into small data. so overloading can be minimized.

HDFS can have a large amount of storage capacity.

HDFS is a linear scalability, realibility and computation of data.

If we write a program in HDFS files, we can use these files several times in a program, no need to write again and again.

It can contain a limited amount of data to be processed.

It can tolerate the faults.

We can measure the data's in terabyte, petabyte, Exabyte.

It can process large amount of data at a time. So it follows the parallel processing. In splitting a program, each part is stored in a particular storage place, later combined the sub sparts.

Disadvantages of using a hadoop:

Managing of cluster in a hadoop is tough.

There are no index pages in a map reduce, so it will make a copy of a full program.

Single master nodes is used to find the limitations.

This program style contains restrictive.

It could not prevent a data's.

HDFS and Map reduce are tough to process.

Conclusions:

Hadoop is very useful for peoples. Especially for business based people such as IBM and many companies. And it is mainly used in Yahoo, Facebook, Twitter etc. Using a hadoop we can make many

inventions, because it is a open source system. It can be used by everyone. The upcoming version of Hadoop is “data hub”, it will bring a common path to use and it is very useful for a customer.

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